

Meal Consumption Frequency in Patients with Type 1 and Type 2 Diabetes

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Abstract—In diabetic individuals, the number of meals is important and long-term irregular food intake may cause hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia complications. The aim of this study was to determine the knowledge levels and consumption status of the patients with Type 1 and Type 2 diabetes. The study included a total of 40 individuals (24 males and 16 females) with diabetes in the province of Sanliurfa, Turkey. The questionnaire was used as the data collection method. The questionnaire was prepared in order to evaluate the frequency, knowledge levels, consumption status and biochemical findings (HbA1c [Hemoglobin A1c], fasting blood glucose) of individuals. It was determined that food preferences were differentiated after diagnosis by type of diabetes. The relationship between diabetes type and number of meals consumed was evaluated. Patients with Type 2 diabetes had higher BMI (Body Mass Index), fasting blood sugar and HbA1c values than patients with Type 1 diabetes. When the number of meals was examined, 50% of Type 1 diabetic patients consumed 6-8 meals, whereas 50% of patients with Type 2 diabetes consumed 4-6 meals ($p = 0.001$). In diabetic patients, blood findings, frequency of food consumption and BMI values vary according to type of diabetes. In the context of diabetes management and control of blood glucose levels, solutions should be studied on regulation of meal consumption.

Keywords—Blood sugar, diabetes, meal, snack.

I. INTRODUCTION

DIABETES mellitus (DM) is a metabolic disease characterized by hyperglycemia, caused by problems of insulin secretion, insulin effects, or both, as a result of genetic and environmental factors and lifestyle changes. After the diagnosis is made, optimal control of blood sugar, careful monitoring of hypertension and the use of antilipidemic drugs should be provided [1]. It can help to detect disease symptoms in patients, to recognize early symptoms, to control the disease and to prevent vascular complications [2]. In patients with Type II diabetes, the risk of coronary artery disease is 2-4 times higher than those without diabetes. 75% of diabetics die from cardiovascular diseases [3]. Many factors, such as the profile of hyperglycemia, timing and amount of food, the amount of carbohydrate in the meal, affect insulin secretion and glucagon secretion [4]. The amount and type of food as well as consumption times are of great importance. Consumption of recommended foods on time and in recommended amounts prevents hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia.

In diabetic patients adequate and balanced nutrition should be taken care of, targeted individual body weight should be reached, meals should not be skipped, the intake times of insulin

or drug amounts should be observed and physical activity level should be increased [5]. Diabetes has become an increasingly important problem in the world. Therefore, it is the responsibility of all health workers in the diabetes treatment team to evaluate diabetes in all respects.

In our study, we aimed to evaluate the effect of diabetes on meal consumption numbers, meal information, purchasing preferences, BMI, fasting blood sugars, HbA1c values in diabetic people living in Sanliurfa, Turkey. It is thought that the information obtained will guide the trainings given to individuals with diabetes.

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

This research was conducted in April 2018 and planned to determine the nutritional knowledge, type of dietary intake and nutrient group consumption of the Type 1 and Type 2 diabetic patients in Sanliurfa, Turkey. The study included 10 individuals with Type 1 diabetes and 30 subjects with Type 2 diabetes on a voluntary basis. In the study; the questionnaire form which was prepared by the researcher was used to determine the level of knowledge about the snack consumption frequency of people with diabetes.

In the evaluation of the findings, SPSS 17.0 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) program was used for statistical analysis. In the evaluation of the study data, descriptive statistical methods (mean, standard deviation), and student-t test were used for comparison of the quantitative data with normal distribution. Significance was evaluated at $p < 0.05$ level.

III. RESULTS

It was found that the mean age of the participants was 41.25 ± 11.367 ; average weight was 75.82 ± 13.65 kg; average height was 170.02 ± 11.61 cm; mean fasting blood glucose was 165.95 ± 52.43 mg/dl; the mean of hemoglobin was 8.12 ± 1.55 and the BMI average was 26.52 ± 3.97 kg/m².

60% ($n = 24$) of the participants were male and 40% ($n = 16$) were female. It was determined that 30% of the participants used multiple insulin treatment, 8% insulin pump and 20% antidiabetic drug, 25% ($n = 10$) of the individuals had Type 1 diabetes and 75% ($n = 30$) had Type 2 diabetes.

55% of diabetics received nutritional counseling, 17.5% of those who received nutritional counseling received it twice a month or once every 3 months, 70% of the participants do not know the carbohydrate count. Table I shows the meal

information of diabetic patients. A significant proportion of diabetic patients were found to have consumed between 4-8 meals.

TABLE I
MEAL INFORMATION

Previously Informing about Snack Consumption	n	%
Yes	27	67.5
No	13	32.5
Person Providing Information About Snack Consumption	n	%
Doctor	7	17.5
Dietitian	16	50.0
Nurse	4	10.0
Qualification of Information	n	%
Yes	20	50.0
No	4	10.0
Partially	3	7.5
Number of Snacks	n	%
3-4	13	32.5

Reason To Consume Snacks	n	%
4-6	21	52.5
6-8	6	15.0
Doctor has mentioned that it is necessary	15	37.5
Not To Fall On Blood Sugar	14	35.0
For Saturation Feeling	11	17.5

It was determined that the number of meals consumed according to the type of diabetes was significantly different ($p = 0.001$). While 83.3% of patients with type 1 diabetes consumed 6-8 meals, 92.3% of Type 2 diabetic patients consumed 3-4 meals.

The mean fasting blood glucose value of Type 2 diabetic patients was significantly higher than the mean of Type 1 diabetic patients ($p=0.008$) (Table II). According to the type of diabetes, fasting blood glucose was differentiated. The mean fasting blood glucose of patients with type 2 diabetes was significantly higher than the mean of Type 1 diabetes patients.

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF FASTING BLOOD SUGAR AND DIABETES

Type of Diabetes	Number of Observations	Mean Fasting Blood Sugar	Std. Deviation	p
Type1 diabetes	10	129.10	39.156	0.008
Type2 diabetes	30	178.23	50.951	

The mean BMI of type 2 diabetic patients was significantly higher than the mean of Type 1 diabetic patients (Table III).

The number of meals consumed by type of diabetes was found to be different. While half of patients with type 1 diabetes consume between 6-8 meals, half of Type 2 diabetic patients consume between 4-6 meals (Table IV).

TABLE III
COMPARISON OF BMI AND DIABETES TYPE

Type of Diabetes	n	Mean BKI	p
Tip 1 diabet	10	21.70 ± 3.22	0.00
Tip 2 diabet	30	28.13 ± 2.68	

TABLE IV
COMPARISON OF DIABETES TYPES WITH DIABETES PATIENTS

		Type of Diabetes		Total	
		Type 1 diabetes	Type 2 diabetes		
Number of consumed meals	3-4	n	1	12	13
		%	7.7	92.3	100.0
	4-6	n	4	17	21
		%	19.0	81.0	100.0
	6-8	n	5	1	6
		%	83.3	16.7	100.0
Total	n	10	30	40	
	%	25.0	75.0	100.0	
Chi-Square p value		0.001			

TABLE V
COMPARISON OF DIABETES TYPES OF DIABETIC PATIENTS WITH DIETARY LABEL INFORMATION

		Type of Diabetes		Total	
		Type 1 diabetes	Type 2 diabetes		
Are Label Information Effective in Your Product Selection?	Yes	n	10	10	20
		%	50	50	100
	No	n	0	20	20
		%	0	100	100
Total	n	10	10	30	
	%	25	25	75	
Chi-Square p value		0.002			

In Table V, when comparing the diabetic products with the food label information, the comparison of type of diabetes with

the effective and non-food products was done by chi-square test. When the results are examined, it is understood that

product selection is effective according to the type of diabetes. Type 1 diabetes is effective in all patients and is effective on half of type 2 diabetic patients.

After the diagnosis of diabetes, food intake preferences were different. It was observed that the preferences of people with type 1 diabetes did not change in those with type 2 diabetes (Table VI).

TABLE VI
COMPARISON OF TYPES OF DIABETES WITH BUYING PREFERENCES

		Type of Diabetes		Total	
		Type 1 diabetes	Type 2 diabetes		
Have Diabetes Change the Preferences of Buying Food After Diagnosis?	Increase	n	7	5	12
		%	58.3	41.7	100
	Decrease	n	2	6	8
		%	25.0	75	100
	Unchange	n	1	19	20
		%	5.0	95	100
Total	n	10	10	30	
	%	25	25	75	
Chi-Square p value			0.003		

Hemoglobin differed according to the type of diabetes. The mean of hemoglobin of type 2 diabetic patients is significantly higher than that of type 1 diabetic patients (Table VII).

TABLE VII
COMPARISON OF HbA1c AND DIABETES TYPE IN DIABETES PATIENTS

Type of Diabetes	n	Mean HbA1c	T-test p value
Type 1 diabetes	10	7.19 ± 1.36	0.026
Type 2 diabetes	30	8.43 ± 1.50	

IV. DISCUSSION

Nutrition is the basic necessity for growth and healthy life starting from the womb to the end of life. In this study, the frequency of snack consumption of Type 1 and Type 2 diabetic individuals was determined and situations experienced in the results were investigated. It was determined that the number of meals consumed according to the type of diabetes varied. While 83.3% of patients with type 1 diabetes consumed 6-8 meals, 92.3% of Type 2 diabetic patients consumed 3-4 meals. Also, food preferences were differentiated after diagnosis according to type of diabetes ($p = 0.003$). When the consumption of snacks was evaluated, it was stated that the group using insulin consumed mid-morning snack more frequently (10%) and 90% of both groups consumed snack. In this study, 75% of the participants were Type 2 and 25% were Type 1 diabetic patients. Approximately half of individuals have diabetes related complications and are treated with insulin. In a study by Uchigata et al., 240 individuals who used OAD (oral antidiabetic) or insulin recorded their meal, contents and times of snack for 1 week. In the results of the study; it was determined that the most skipped meal in both groups was breakfast (8.6%) [6]. In this research, it was determined that the most skipped meals were lunch (36%). In a study by Mekary et al., the effects of eating frequency and snacking on the risk of type 2 diabetes were examined. During the follow-up period 1944 (total 29206) type 2 diabetes was diagnosed. It is stated

that those who skip breakfast meals are at 21% higher risk of type 2 diabetes. Individuals consuming 1-2 meals per day were found to be at higher risk for type 2 diabetes than individuals consuming 3 meals a day [7].

In this study, 67.5% of the participants were informed by dietitians about the consumption of snack. A significant proportion of diabetic patients were found to have consumed between 4-8 meals. The majority of snack consumption is due to health problems. Frequent feeding delay hunger at the next meal, resulting in a more controlled and less nutrient intake. Therefore, when the right choices are made, the snack positively affects the blood glucose level [8]. In a study conducted by El Khoury et al. [9], 20 healthy male individuals consumed 5 different snacks (plain yogurt, plain yogurt and honey, strawberry yogurt, skimmed milk or orange juice) as a mid-morning snack. Nutrient intake was evaluated after 120 minutes. Blood glucose, serum insulin and subjective satiety were measured before and after meals. The pre-meal glucose response was diminished in a dose-dependent manner to increased protein and reduced sugar in the milk.

The ratio of protein to carbohydrate is reported to be negatively correlated with glucose before meal as it improves insulin action rather than increasing insulin concentration. Compared to orange juice, it has been reported that blood glucose is lower after a snack of dairy products. It has been found that skimmed milk with the lowest protein carbohydrate ratio among dairy products reduces glucose before and after meals without causing high insulin levels. No effect on appetite has been identified [9]. In this study, the most frequently preferred option of snacks is "fruit", "nuts" and "bread-cheese". In our study, half of the patients with Type 1 diabetes consume between 6-8 meals, while half of the patients with Type 2 diabetes consume between 4-6 meals. It is understood that food preferences are differentiated after diagnosis by type of diabetes. Type 1 diabetes has increased in a significant proportion of patients, while Type 2 diabetes has not changed.

Diabetes has become an increasingly important problem in the world. Therefore, it is the responsibility of all health workers in the diabetes treatment team to evaluate diabetes in all respects. Improving the quality of life of the patient during the entire treatment process is still a duty of the diabetes treatment team. Clinical use of scales such as DRPA (Diabetes Related Problematic Areas) is thought to be effective in the psychological approach and re-planning of treatment due to individual requirements. However, it is a fact that there is a need for more studies with large samples. In this study, the frequency of snack consumption was determined in Type 1 and Type 2 DM subjects and the conditions were investigated.

In the study, the following suggestions were made within the framework of the findings; Medical nutrition therapy, including lifestyle changes and healthy eating habits, which form the basis of the treatment of people with diabetes, should be lifelong applications. In this context, they can use energy-free sweeteners approved by FDA (Food and Drug Administration) in their beverages and desserts at home. Those who want to control weight, obese and diabetics may include sweeteners in their daily diet, provided that they do not exceed the maximum

use doses specified for each sweetener. The use of low-calorie or non-caloric sweeteners can be used to limit dietary sugar consumption and calorie intake. Diabetics also can use because they do not increase their blood sugar. Although diabetic products sold in the market contain sweeteners instead of sugar, they also contain high amounts of fat, flour, etc. Due to their content calories may also be high. Therefore, individuals should be trained to change the perception of unlimited use of such products. It should be kept in mind that excessive consumption of sugar alcohols may cause gastrointestinal problems.

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